

AURICULOTHERAPY IN THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF CHILDREN WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

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Abstract. *Cerebral infantile paralysis is a disease that develops as a result of damage to motor centres or motor pathways in infectious lesions or traumas of the brain. The disease is accompanied by increased muscle tone (tension), as a result of which the child is unable to make active movements. Often when trying to make any movement there are violent involuntary movements, so-called athetosis (from Greek athetos - unstable), further aggravating the patient's condition. Causes of cerebral palsy are polyetiological: infection (whooping cough, diphtheria, measles, influenza, etc.), birth trauma (in case of prolonged heavy labour, rapid birth, etc.), in case of prematurity of children. (5) A number of prenatal, intrapartum and postnatal factors are involved in the occurrence of cerebral palsy. CNS damage leading to the formation of cerebral palsy may be caused by the following factors; anoxia, asphyxia and/or hypoxia; prematurity, low birth weight and intrauterine developmental delay (IUCD); intrauterine infection, haemolytic disease of the newborn (HBN), maternal thrombophilia, anomalous brain development and its destructive changes, etc. Chromosomal defects may have a certain significance.*

Keywords: *cerebral palsy, auriculotherapy, auricular points.*

According to O'Shen M (2008), among premature babies with extremely low birth weight the risk of cerebral palsy formation increases 100-fold. In the Russian Federation, in accordance with the classification of cerebral palsy developed and proposed by Semenova K.A. et al. (1973), it is customary to distinguish the following types of cerebral palsy: - spastic diplegia; - double hemiplegia; - hemiplegia; - hyperkinetic form; - atonic-astatic form; - mixed form of cerebral palsy. According to the current ICD-10, 7 types of cerebral palsy are considered: - spastic cerebral palsy (double hemiplegia, tetraplegia), - spastic diplegia (Little's syndrome), - infantile hemiplegia (hemiplegic form), - dyskinetic cerebral palsy (dystonic, hyperkinetic), - ataxic cerebral palsy (atonic-astatic form), - other type of cerebral palsy (mixed forms), - unspecified cerebral palsy. (7, 9) There are other variants of classification abroad. In particular, Panteliadis C.P. and Korinthenberg R. (2005) distinguish spastic forms of cerebral palsy (spastic hemiplegia and bilateral spastic cerebral palsy: predominantly lower limbs, total, triplegia, dyskinetic-spastic), dyskinetic (predominantly dystonia or athetosis) and ataxic (non-progressive congenital cerebellar infection and ataxia). According to the recommendations of some authors, ataxic forms of cerebral palsy are included in the dyskinetic group.

Characteristic signs of spastic diplegia include: - spastic tetraparesis with lesions of the lower limbs; - delayed development of the motor sphere; - characteristic gait - hips turned inwards, knees joined; - oculomotor disorders - strabismus, decreased visual acuity; - hearing disorders; - delayed speech development - noted in 80% of patients. Mental development in this form of cerebral palsy suffers less than in other cases. Oligophrenia occurs in 20% of children with spastic diplegia. The prognosis in the motor sphere is not very favourable. Only every fourth patient can move independently, and with pronounced tetraparesis, the patient is forced to be in a wheelchair. If mental abilities are preserved, patients can be educated along with healthy children.

Hemiplegia - in this form of cerebral palsy, half of the body is affected. This form of the disease is second only to spastic diplegia in the degree of spread. It is most often found in premature infants or in children who have suffered intracranial head trauma during childbirth. The risk of hemiplegia increases with abnormalities of the placental circulation, placental abruption, immunological conflict between the foetus and the mother. In hemiplegia, severe gait disturbances, physical and mental retardation, and convulsive seizures are noticeable.

Double hemiplegia is the most severe and rare form of the disease, with profound musculoskeletal damage and severe mental retardation. Children diagnosed with this type of cerebral palsy are unable to sit, walk, serve themselves, and have a complete lack of speech and its understanding. Children with this diagnosis are capable of primitive emotional reactions, such as recognising and being happy with their parents, but they are unable to master even simple skills and cannot learn. Treatment is aimed at general relief of the patient's condition and maximising their quality of life.

Hyperkinetic form - risk factors for hyperkinetic type of cerebral palsy include haemolytic disease complicated by jaundice, early delivery, infectious diseases of the mother, low birth weight. Symptoms of this type of cerebral palsy are manifested in a delay in the development of motor activity. The child is marked by lethargy in movements, spinal abnormalities, incorrect positioning of the legs. Mental development is usually not affected, the child develops well intellectually, successfully adapts to life in society. This type of cerebral palsy is diagnosed in 20-25% of patients.

Ataxic form. Children with this rare form of the disease suffer from a lack of coordination in walking, they find it difficult to perform fast and precise movements. The ataxic form occurs in only 6% of patients and is due to cerebellar damage. Other possible causes of pathology include cerebral hypoxia caused by insufficient blood flow in the placenta or abnormal labour. When walking, the child staggers, spreads his legs too wide. He has difficulty performing various tasks that require well-developed hand motor skills, such as buttoning buttons or lacing shoes. Another characteristic sign is hand tremor, which increases when trying to pick up an object or perform an action. Children with this diagnosis inevitably suffer from speech, mental retardation may be observed. Children with ataxic form of cerebral palsy do not lend themselves well to learning, they have unreasonable aggression, seizures, epileptic attacks. At an early stage of the disease there are difficulties in diagnosing its forms. It is easiest to determine the spastic form, usually it happens in the first six months after birth. Hemiplegia and ataxic forms usually manifest themselves in the 5th-7th month of the child's life. Most often pay attention to neurological disorders, unreasonable excitability, poor coordination, delayed physical development. Hyperkinetic form is diagnosed after a year. When performing the diagnosis of cerebral palsy, it is important to exclude diseases with similar symptoms. This is autism, brain lesions of a traumatic nature, childhood schizophrenia. Cerebral palsy is not a progressive disease. (2)

The main complex therapy of cerebral palsy is a team approach realised using different types of treatment. Medication therapy is aimed at restoring lost and deficit neurological functions and consists in the use of various groups of pharmaceuticals: vascular (vinpocetine, cinnarizine, etc.), nootropic (piracetam, et al.), nootropic (piracetam, etc.), neurometabolic (calcium gopantenate), neuropeptide (cerebramine, semax, etc.), amino acid (glycine, acetylaminoyanthanoic acid, etc.), myorelaxants (tolperisone, lioresal, etc.), botulinum toxin preparations), botulinum toxin preparations (Botox, Dysport), mixed-spectrum complexes

(Cortexin, etc.), vitamins (mono- and multivitamins) and minerals. (6;7) Of the non-medicamentous methods of therapy, therapeutic physical training, massage, orthopedic correction methods, physiotherapy (isolated or in combination with drug therapy), dynamic proprioceptive correction, hippotherapy are widely used. (9;10) There are also methods of treatment with reflexotherapy. There is both corporal acupuncture and auriculotherapy, i.e. a method of treatment by acting on biologically active points on the ear drum.

Auriculotherapy is one of the methods of oriental reflexotherapy through irritation of active points of the auricle. These points are located in a certain pattern and do not manifest themselves in a healthy person. The skin of the auricle is normally painless. Auricular point, according to modern ideas, has an area of about two millimetres; histological studies have not revealed any specific structure. In a healthy person, these points are as if latent and manifest themselves only in the presence of a pathological process in the body. In acute diseases certain points (corresponding) become painful when pressed, in chronic diseases the skin of the auricle in the corresponding area (zone) acquires some changes: peeling, scales, tubercles, hyperaemia, etc. appear. When the functions of the organ are normalised, the pathophysiological properties of the point disappear and it becomes latent again. (1;8) Auricular points are places on the surface of the auricle that interact with internal organs, channels, tissues and all parts of the body. Special points located on the lines, grooves and surface of the auricle with which diagnoses and treatment of diseases can be performed are called acupuncture points of the ear. Auricular diagnostics is an auxiliary method of diagnosis, which is based on various positive reactions (deformation, colour changes, peeling, pimples, vascular changes, sensitivity on palpation, changes in the electrical characteristics of the skin, etc.). Positive reactions appear in the corresponding zone of the auricle in case of pathology in a certain organ or part of the body. Auricular therapy involves external action on the corresponding points of the auricle with acupuncture, pressure, injection, bloodletting and patch application for the prevention and treatment of diseases. Since auriculotherapy originated a long time ago, it has a long history in China and abroad.

Treatment by means of acupuncture to the points of the auricle (er-chzhen-liao) as well as corporate acupuncture has been used since ancient times among the peoples of the East and in Egypt (5-3 century BC).

In 1973, during an archaeological excavation in Hunan Province, Changsha in the third tomb of the Han Dynasty, the ear meridians connected with the upper limbs, eyes, cheeks, and throat were described in the silk letters 'Canon of Cauterisation of Eleven Yin and Yang Vessels'. In the 'Yellow Emperor's Treatise on the Internal', the 'ear meridian' is considered to be the meridian of the three parts of the torso, and the physiological and pathological relationship of the ear with meridians, internal organs, and various parts of the body is also described in more detail. For example, in the 'Canon of Mysterious Essence' (the oldest surviving work of Chinese medicine), in the chapter 'Emergence of diseases from the impact of harmful energy on internal organs' it is said that the circulation of Qi and Blood in 12 channels and 365 collaterals first reaches the face, and then enters the various orifices. The purified Yang energy rises upwards and enters the eyes, by which they see. A separate stream of energy rises up and enters the ear, by virtue of which they hear. This book also states that 'The ear is the place where the meridians of the whole body meet'.

Records of auricular acupuncture and its application have been seen in Greece and Ancient Egypt. The famous ancient Greek physician Hippocrates treated male infertility and impotence by

drawing blood from the ear. Hippocrates also discovered that the outer ear is linked to a person's depression. In ancient Egypt, ear acupuncture was used to sterilise women. Chinese acupuncture and moxibustion penetrated France in the 17th century, a native of Lyon, physician, surgeon Paul Nogier studied acupuncture. In 1957, Nogier published his first article in a German journal on acupuncture. He developed the topography of the auricle as an inverted embryo in the womb, and the number of auricular points was increased to 42. This event started the rapid spread of auricular therapy in Germany and other countries, attracting more and more attention from scientific circles around the world. Although auricular acupuncture has a long history, but due to the conservative views of the feudal system, discrimination of Chinese traditional medicine during the semi-feudal and semi-colonial rule of the state, auricular acupuncture could not show itself in all its splendour, although it was spread among the people. In 1956, in Laixi County, Shandong Province, an article published on 'Treatment of Acute Tonsillitis by Auricular Therapy' fully reflects the environment of application of auricular acupuncture among the common people. In 1958, Mr Ye Xiaolin translated into Chinese an article by Paul Nogier on auricular points, which was published in the 12th issue of 'Shanghai Journal of Traditional Chinese Medicine' with the title 'New Discoveries on Auricular Therapy in Foreign Countries'. This publication immediately aroused great interest from Chinese medical practitioners of acupuncture and moxibustion. Medical practitioners all over the country began to work hard to conduct theoretical and clinical research based on the achievements of their predecessors, which led to a qualitative leap in auricular diagnosis and therapy.

In 1982, the Chinese Acupuncture and Moxotherapy Association, on behalf of the Western Pacific Office of the World Health Organization, assisted WHO in developing the standardisation of auricular point terms. Chinese researchers on auricular points have fully studied, collected ancient literature and folk experiences, and borrowed foreign research experience. Thanks to them, numerous Chinese data on ear acupuncture points collected over the past 50 years on clinical diagnosis and treatment, acupuncture anaesthesia and laboratory research have been arranged. From 1982 to 1987, the Chinese Acupuncture and Moxotherapy Association conducted a trial application of the project. Eventually in 1987, a preliminary draft was provided at the first World Health Organisation West Pacific meeting on the standardisation of auricular acupuncture terminologies. Later, for various reasons, the work of the World Health Organisation group stopped at written communication and discussion. To date, no generally accepted, complete draft has been developed to standardise ear acupuncture terminology. Since the Chinese Acupuncture and Moxotherapy Association published a draft on the standardisation of ear acupuncture points in 1988, it has been initially applied in medical, teaching, research, publishing, and scientific communication within and outside the country. On 16 October 1992, the State Administration of Technical Control approved the 'National Acupuncture Point Standard - 92', which was implemented on 1 May 1993. After 14 years of application of this standard, the State Administration of Traditional Medicine again drafted the 'Additional Amendments to the National Standard on Names and Locations of Auricular Points'. Between 2006 and 2007, the first amendments to the 'National Standard on Auricular Points-92' were made. The General State Administration of Quality Supervision, Inspection and Quarantine of the People's Republic of China, in conjunction with the State Standardisation Committee, published the 'National Standard of the People's Republic of China on Names and Locations of Auricular Points' (GB/T1373420, 'National Standard on Auricular Points'), which noticed the 'National Standard on Auricular

Points-92' (GBT1371992). This standard has been implemented since 1 July 2008. In May 2013, the standard 'Naming and Location of Ear Acupuncture Points' became an international industry standard of the World Federation of Acupuncture and Moxibustion Associations. The National Auricular Point Standard is the result of free competition between scientists in the field of auricular diagnosis and therapy, which is of high significance. This standard is a worldwide language of communication in auricular therapy, training, research and development, and it also provides a basic knowledge for beginners. Auriculotherapy has a wide range of indications, it is used not only for pain elimination and treatment of neurasthenia, vegetative disorders, other functional diseases, but also has a good therapeutic effect in the following diseases: gastritis, enteritis, ulcers, hyperplasia, stones in the liver, gallbladder, kidneys, etc. It has a good therapeutic effect on bacteria, viruses, protozoa and other infectious diseases such as acute/chronic bronchitis, allergic diseases: allergic asthma, allergic rhinitis, etc. Currently, according to preliminary calculations of the World Health Organisation, there are more than 249 types of diseases that are treated with auriculotherapy. Auriculotherapy has been shown to be highly effective in treating more than 70 kinds of diseases. (4) The theory of biogeography was proposed by Zhang Yingqing in 1973. He found that the second metacarpal bone of a human being is similar to a reduced snapshot of the human body, he put forward the view that acupuncture points are a group of cells with similarity to certain organs in substance and chemical structure. The chemical composition of each point of a relatively independent part of the body has a high similarity with the chemical composition of the corresponding part of the organism it represents. According to the theory of biogeography, the auricle is a projection of the whole body, contains information about each organ and part of an organism. Therefore, regarding the principle of information transmission to auricular points, some specialists have proposed the mechanism of holographic reflection. According to the theory of biogeography, in clinical practice we can identify pathological changes of internal organs according to the changes of colour and shape of zones on the auricle. The auricle is not only related to physiological activity of internal organs, it also reflects pathological changes occurring in the body. Therefore, by stimulating the different zones of the ear it is possible to regulate the work of organs and tissues. There are 12 pairs of cranial nerves in the human body, 6 of which are directly connected to the ear. Western medicine believes that as long as the organism lives in a certain environment, metabolic processes take place and when its internal or external environment changes, the organism automatically reacts accordingly to adapt to the changes in the environment. For the human body, the most important method of regulation is nerve regulation. The response to changes in the internal and external environment is called a reflex. Reflex is the basic form of nervous activity. From neuroanatomy we can see the dense distribution of nerves along the auricle: the great auricular nerve, the small occipital nerve, the facial nerve, the lingual nerve, etc. The great auricular nerve and the small occipital nerve belong to the branches of the cervical plexus (C2,C3), connected to the spinal nerves of the central nervous system. The trigeminal nerve, vagus nerve, facial nerve, lingopharyngeal nerve are part of the first and second pair of cranial nerves and are closely connected with the cerebral cortex. The trigeminal nerve, in addition to transmitting sensory information to the brain, is also connected to the spinal cord via the spinal nerve in the varicose bridge. Thus, the nerves on the auricle are connected directly to the central nervous system, the highest section of the nerve centre: the brain, the cerebral cortex, the spinal cord, etc. In terms of the circulation of Qi and Blood through the meridians, the six Yang meridians either enter the ear or pass around the ear. The six Yin meridians connect to the ear through the

connecting branches of the channels or reach the ear after the branches merge with the Yang meridians. Thus, all 12 meridians have a direct or indirect connection to the ear. (4;8)

Mental retardation is one of the major associated symptoms of cerebral palsy in children. Children with cerebral palsy with mental retardation have worse cognition, understanding and acceptance than normal children, and the effects of rehabilitation treatment are worse than children with cerebral palsy without mental retardation. Therefore, improving the intellectual level of children with cerebral palsy is an important part of cerebral palsy rehabilitation.

Traditional Chinese medicine classifies cerebral palsy into the categories of ‘impotence’, ‘five slowness’, ‘five softness’ and ‘five hardness’.

Traditional Chinese Medicine believes that “the head is the house of wisdom.” It is located in the upper part of the human body and contains the brain. This is the residence of the human body and the location of the clear opening dominate life and basic neural consciousness and sensorimotor functions. Scalp acupuncture is a type of acupuncture therapy based on the theory of traditional Chinese medicine and modern reflex theory.

It has the function of moving Si and blood, deepening the meridians, and adjusting yin and yang. Modern medical research suggests that scalp acupuncture can increase blood flow, improve the hypoxic state of the cerebral cortex, and increase the blood oxygen supply to brain tissue. The bioholographic theory believes that the shape of the human ear is similar to the shape of a fetus in the womb. In this study, the auricular points were chosen as the main points: heart, kidneys, back of the head and Shenmen.

This study shows that adding scalp acupuncture and auriculotherapy to overall treatment is more effective than standard treatment. Cerebral palsy primarily refers to non-progressive brain damage caused by various causes within one month after birth. The main clinical manifestation is a movement disorder, accompanied by mental retardation, sensory impairment, epilepsies. Mental retardation is one of the common complications of cerebral palsy, which has a high incidence rate. People with intellectual disabilities live with reduced learning abilities, and their rehabilitation treatment is more complex than for other children. In recent years, the clinical application of scalp acupuncture has achieved good results. However, the use of scalp acupuncture alone can no longer meet clinical needs. More and more emphasis is being placed on comprehensive treatment plans based on scalp acupuncture in combination with other treatment modalities. Auriculotherapy, as an important part of traditional Chinese medicine therapy, has broad prospects for use in the rehabilitation treatment of children with cerebral palsy. This study combines scalp acupuncture and auriculotherapy to observe its effectiveness in children with cerebral palsy and mental retardation. (3)

Auricular therapy includes acupuncture, electroacupuncture, acupressure, lasering, cauterization, moxibustion, and bloodletting in the auricle. For 2500 years, people have employed auricular therapy for treating diseases, but the methods have been limited to bloodletting and cauterization. Only after 1957, the international scientific community became aware that the map of the ear resembles an inverted fetus, its introduction has led to auricular acupuncture (AA) becoming a more systemic approach, and, following the identification and standardization of more precise points, AA has been employed in clinical applications. The mechanisms of AA are considered to have a close relationship with the autonomic nervous system, the neuroendocrine system, neuroimmunological factors, neuroinflammation, and neural reflex, as well as antioxidation. Auricular therapy has been applied, for example, for pain relief, for the treatment of

epilepsy, anxiety, and obesity, and for improving sleep quality. However, the mechanisms and evidence for auricular therapy warrant further study. (13)

To observe and evaluate a method that is effective and practical for treatment of cerebral palsied (CP) children in China. The patient's age and disease type and individual specific conditions were considered in choosing therapy methods accordingly: Chinese herbs, acupuncture, auricular seed pressure, point finger pressing, massage, orthopedic hand manipulation, physiotherapy, occupational therapy, language therapy, etc. Meanwhile we created a new CP treatment model that combines hospitalized treatment with family therapy. The majority of CP patients improved greatly in motor and social adaptation capacities after treatment. Wilcoxon paired rank sum test analysis showed that there were significant differences between the data before and after treatment ($P < 0.01$). This combined therapy method, based on traditional Chinese medicine and western medicine plus family supplemental therapy, is an effective and practical treatment strategy for CP children in China. (11)

To manage chemotherapy-induced neuropathy (CIN), this paper explores reliable and valid objectives measures to evaluate the treatment effects of auricular point acupressure (APA). This study was a repeated-measures one-group design. Participants received four weeks of APA to manage their CIN. The laboratory-assessed and objective outcomes included quantitative sensory testing, grip and pinch strength, and inflammatory biomarkers. Wilcoxon matched pairs signed-rank tests were conducted to determine change scores of outcomes at pre- vs. post- and pre- vs. 1-month follow-up. Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was used to examine the linear association of score changes of all objective study outcomes. Comparing pre-and-post APA, (1) the mean score of the monofilament for all lower extremity sites tested decreased after APA, indicating sensory improvement; (2) the suprathreshold pinprick stimuli mean scores on the upper extremities increased, except the scores from the index finger and thumb; (3) the pain tolerance of thumb and trapezius areas increased; (4) decreasing $IL1\beta$ ($p = .05$), $IFN\gamma$ ($p = .02$), $IL-2$ ($p = .03$), $IL-6$ ($p = .05$), $IL-10$ ($p = .05$), and $IP10/CXCL10$ ($p = .04$) were observed pre-post APA. Conditional pain modulation was significantly ($p < .05$) associated with pain intensity ($r = 0.55$), tingling ($r = 0.59$); and $IL1\beta$ concentration ($r = 0.53$) pre-post APA. The sustained effects of 4-week APA were observed at the 1-month follow-up. Our study findings demonstrated the promising effectiveness of APA in the management of CIN, and these treatment effects can be assessed using reliable and valid objective measures. If the efficacy of APA to manage CIN is confirmed in a larger sample, APA has the potential to be a scalable treatment for CIN because it is a reproducible, standardized, and easy-to-perform intervention. (12)

Since auricular acupuncture is a diagnostic and treatment system based on normalizing the body's dysfunction, auricular acupuncture has been applied for pain relief, relaxation, and so on. These techniques would modulate the autonomic nerve system, thereby inducing the above-mentioned effects. The aim was to see the effect of auricular acupuncture applied to the "Shenmen" and "Point Zero" points on the postoperative heart rate variability (HRV). Twenty-six patients who underwent hemicolectomy under general anesthesia were randomized into the control or the acupuncture group. After the operation and before emergence, the acupuncture group received auricular acupuncture. An electrocardiographic unit was placed for recording the autonomic nervous activities.

Results. The low frequency (LF)/high frequency (HF) ratio of HRV increased ($P = 0.0007$) in the control, but the ratio in the acupuncture did not change. There were significant differences

between the ratios of the two groups at 3 : 00, 4 : 00, and 5 : 00. HF of the acupuncture group tended to be higher. HFs of the acupuncture group were significantly higher than those of the control group at 3 : 00, 4 : 00, and 5 : 00. Auricular acupuncture kept the LF/HF ratio at lower levels and HF at higher levels during postoperative period in the patients who had undergone hemicolectomy. (14).

Conclusions: Thus, summing up the literature review, it can be noted that despite the relevance of the problem of treatment with reflexology for cerebral palsy, it has clearly not been sufficiently studied and covered in the literature. There is no reliable data on treatment with the auriculotherapy method in various places around the world, and the mechanism of reflexology has been poorly studied.

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